

1 I214F, 10 I214T, 2 I214V, 2 T214I



0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 I214F, 10 I214T, 2 I214V, 2 T214I



- I
- T
- V
- F

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 I214F, 10 I214T, 2 I214V, 2 T214I



- I
- T
- V
- F

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 I214F, 10 I214T, 2 I214V, 2 T214I



- I
- T
- V
- F

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12